

1 **Determination of kinase addiction by quantitative methods.**

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6 Kinase activation is one method by which tumor cells drive the oncogenic gene expression program.
7 Resistance is a challenge to the use of existing chemotherapies and to the development of novel
8 chemotherapies. Compensatory signal transduction through resistance-associated kinase activation has
9 been described; approaches to discovery of the precise kinases by which resistance is imparted to cancer
10 cells undergoing active kinase inhibition are technically advanced and require gain- and/or loss-of-function
11 genetic analyses. Oncogenic Ras pathway Raf kinase mutant BRAF V600E is a driver of melanoma. We
12 studied Braf kinase inhibition in melanoma cells by measuring and studying total transcription following
13 pharmacologic inhibition of BrafV600E in melanoma cells with vemurafenib. Quantitative study of whole
14 transcriptome gene expression changes following chemical inhibition of BrafV600E with RNA-sequencing
15 was sufficient to identify MAP3K8/COT as an up-regulated kinase that functioned in compensatory
16 signaling following oncogenic kinase inhibition in the transformed cellular context. Measurement of total
17 transcription was sufficient to identify induction of VDAC3 in human cells expressing oncogenic KRas
18 G12V, which had previously been identified using a chemical biologic approach employed to discover
19 synthetic lethal interactions in KRas mutant cancer. The approach described here has wide applicability,
20 specifically towards identification of kinase and phosphatase vulnerabilities in non-perturbed and
21 perturbed cancer settings.
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Results

We studied the melanoma transcriptome to determine if kinase addiction could be quantitatively determined at the systems level, measuring total transcription in 8 separate vemurafenib-sensitive melanoma cell lines, and comparing this to vemurafenib-resistant cell lines, paired for each of the 8 vemurafenib-sensitive settings.

Figure 1: Whole transcriptome technologies can identify MAP3K8 as a transcriptional determinant of resistance to kinase inhibition.

n=8

A375	vemurafenib-sensitive
SK-MEL-28	vemurafenib-sensitive
K4	vemurafenib-sensitive
SK-MEL-27	vemurafenib-sensitive
UACC903	vemurafenib-sensitive
WM1205	vemurafenib-sensitive
WM164	vemurafenib-sensitive
MGH-CH-1	vemurafenib-sensitive

n=8

A375	vemurafenib-resistant
SK-MEL-28	vemurafenib-resistant
K4	vemurafenib-resistant
SK-MEL-27	vemurafenib-resistant
UACC903	vemurafenib-resistant
WM1205	vemurafenib-resistant
WM164	vemurafenib-resistant
MGH-CH-1	vemurafenib-resistant

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1326	6.30e-03	0.626	-2.7319879	-1.7108206	25.58	MAP3K8	765/15399	95.0

Johannessen and Garraway identified *MAP3K8* (COT) as a kinase that functioned in compensatory kinase signaling by individually transducing melanoma cells with hundreds of kinase ORFs and measuring cancer cell survival (viability) for each ORF transduction in the presence of vemurafenib.

Ectopic kinase expression for discovery of resistance-associated genes was associated with differential viability (percent cell survival following kinase expression and BRAF chemical inhibition) (Johannessen and Garraway, 2011). For example, COT expression in BRAF V600E mutant A375 cells was associated with approximately 50% viability, as compared to SK-MEL-28 cells, also BRAF V600E mutant, where COT expression was associated with cell survival (viability) at approximately 80-90% (Johannessen and Garraway, 2011).

A model that views intrinsic tumor gene expression at baseline or in response to a pharmacologic intervention (kinase inhibition) as a primary determinant of some biologic property - whether therapeutic potential/index or resistance - suggests RNA-sequencing or microarray-based determination of percent differential expression transcriptome-wide (the magnitude of change in kinase gene expression following exposure to the BRAF inhibitor vemurafenib when comparing all genes expressed) can be used to quantitatively discover gene products sought after using gain- or loss-of-function discovery endeavors.

Thus, we measured total expression in A375 cells and in SK-MEL-28 cells following 8 hours of exposure to vemurafenib *in vitro*. Differential expression of MAP3K8 (COT) in A375 cells following a brief exposure to vemurafenib was at 20.9%, while MAP3K8 expression in SK-MEL-28 following an identical vemurafenib exposure (in a second BRAF V600E mutant melanoma cell line) was at 58.1%. While short-term vemurafenib treatment of A375 cells was associated with a relatively marginal transcriptional induction of MAP3K8, identical vemurafenib treatment of SK-MEL-28 cells resulted in transcriptional induction of MAP3K8 that measured greater than nearly 60% of the transcriptome. Thus, quantitative study of total transcription using whole transcriptome technologies was capable of discerning a differential cell survival response that correlated with a compensatory change in MAP3K8 expression that accordingly more or less significant.

Figure 2: Whole transcriptome technologies can quantitatively discern MAP3K8 induction levels as a transcriptional correlate of differential resistance *in vitro* following forced kinase expression.

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n=6 A375 (DMSO; control; 8 hours)
n=6 A375 (vemurafenib; 125 nM; 8 hours)

n=3 SK-MEL-28 (DMSO; control; 8 hours)
n=3 SK-MEL-28 (vemurafenib; 125 nM; 8 hours)

A375

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
ILMN_1741159	8.08e-01	-0.2470527	-5.4805	-0.03041841	MAP3K8	37317/47187	20.9

SK-MEL-28

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
ILMN_1741159	5.06e-01	-0.6791284	-5.2751	-0.11506891	MAP3K8	19775/47187	58.1

Consistent with our findings, COT expression was predictive of resistance to vemurafenib in a panel of cancer cell lines at baseline (Johannessen and Garraway, 2011).

To validate whether this quantitative approach to discovery of therapeutic vulnerabilities and drivers of resistance in response to pharmacologic intervention in cellular systems whose output was measured most usually as survival or death (synthetic lethal interactions), we measured total transcription in HBec bronchial epithelial cells of the human lung following ectopic expression of oncogenic mutant KRas G12V. VDAC3 was transcriptionally activated following short-term KRas G12V expression to an extent greater than 90% of the transcriptome.

Figure 3: A synthetic lethal interaction between VDAC3 and oncogenic KRas can be identified using whole transcriptome technologies.

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	logFC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
7419	2.06E-08	0.0745	-5.606602	-0.4179301	4338.2	VDAC3	1291/17273	92.5

1 Finally, we evaluated whether the whole transcriptome method of quantitative determination of
 2 kinase addiction in resistance to therapy following administration of a kinase inhibitor or in the acute
 3 transcriptional response to therapeutic kinase inhibition that we demonstrated could also similarly to
 4 functional and chemical genomic methods to blindly retrieve the identity of genes that functioned in
 5 synthetic lethal fashion in the KRas G12V background might be a broadly applicable methodology in
 6 discernment of the identity of genes functionally relevant to the study of complex biological questions, we
 7 studied the BRCA1 deficient genetic background. The BRCA1 deficient background remains incompletely
 8 understood with respect to mechanisms of action that underlie enhanced tumorigenesis resulting from the
 9 failure to control transformation in humans with germline mutations in BRCA1 or BRCA2; separate but
 10 related to study of BRCA1/2 deficient backgrounds in humans with germline mutation of these genes,
 11 studying the major mechanism of action(s) by which BRCA1/2 function in DNA repair processes that are
 12 relevant to cancer therapeutics like the -parib family of PARP inhibitors for which a suggested mechanism
 13 of action is a synthetic lethal interaction following PARP1 inhibition in BRCA1/2 deficient cells that results
 14 in a switch in cell death signaling resulting in activation of cell death in BRCA1/2-deficient cells but whose
 15 broader mechanistic functioning in cancer therapy remains incompletely understood.

10 Mengwasser and Elledge utilized functional genetic screening methodology to study BRCA1
 11 function and identified FEN1 and APEX1/2 as synthetic lethal targets in BRCA1-deficient cells. Thus, we
 12 measured total gene expression in breast tissues from humans with endogenous mutation of BRCA1 and
 13 measured transcriptome-wide gene expression changes resulting from BRCA1 mutation using data
 14 produced by an Illumina expression beadchip (microarray), directly in the human breast, from humans with
 15 endogenous (actual) mutation of BRCA1, and without further processing (i.e., lacking functional readout
 16 like a measure of cell death separate from percent differential expression of the gene determined based
 17 on magnitude of change in expression of the gene with respect to all other genes in the transcriptome,
 18 globally). In this experimental setting, while identity of targets that function in a synthetic lethal manner
 19 with BRCA1 mutation are not as easily discerned, as only activated MAP kinase targets are considered in
 20 the prior biological context, not only do the the nature of targets: a flap structure-specific endonuclease,
 21 and an apurinic/aprimidinic endodeoxyribonuclease indicate nevertheless that the methodology
 22 possessed enough power to blindly identify a genomic target that functioned together with BRCA1 in
 23 BRCA1-deficient settings (only three endonucleases in total were among the top 5% most differentially
 24 expressed genes in the breast tissue of humans with BRCA1 mutation in pre-cancer: FEN1, and two other
 25 endonucleases, SLX1B and EXOG, which was differentially expressed but repressed).

19 GSE17072

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
ILMN_1755834	0.03430001	-2.32588305	-3.5296	-0.47492763	FEN1	2135/	
ILMN_1661886	0.02553046	-2.47652115	-3.3456	-0.41336766	APEX1	1588/	
ILMN_1652505	0.14341734	-1.5431615	-4.4049	-0.29607592	APEX2	8598/48803	

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References

Johannessen, C.M., Boehm, J.S., Kim, S.Y., Thomas, S.R., Wardwell, L., Johnson, L.A., Emery, C.M., Stransky, N., Cogdill, A.P., Barretina, J. and Caponigro, G., 2010. COT drives resistance to RAF inhibition through MAP kinase pathway reactivation. *Nature*, 468(7326), pp.968-972.

Yang, W.S. and Stockwell, B.R., 2008. Synthetic lethal screening identifies compounds activating iron-dependent, nonapoptotic cell death in oncogenic-RAS-harboring cancer cells. *Chemistry & biology*, 15(3), pp.234-245.

Yagoda, N., Von Rechenberg, M., Zaganjor, E., Bauer, A.J., Yang, W.S., Fridman, D.J., Wolpaw, A.J., Smukste, I., Peltier, J.M., Boniface, J.J. and Smith, R., 2007. RAS–RAF–MEK-dependent oxidative cell death involving voltage-dependent anion channels. *Nature*, 447(7146), pp.865-869.

Mengwasser, K.E., Adeyemi, R.O., Leng, Y., Choi, M.Y., Clairmont, C., D’Andrea, A.D. and Elledge, S.J., 2019. Genetic screens reveal FEN1 and APEX2 as BRCA2 synthetic lethal targets. *Molecular cell*, 73(5), pp.885-899.